

ISic0719

I.Sicily inscription 0719

Language

Latin

Type

unknown

Material

marble

Object

balustrade

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

2014.09.25

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Catina

Place of origin (modern)

Catania

Provenance

Assumed to come from the theatre (in store in a box labelled 'marmi provenienti dall'Antiquarium')

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Catania, Teatro Romano di Catania, inventory 5937

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height 20.5 cm

Width 32.8 cm

Depth 5.4-6.0 cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: 78 mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: not available mm

Text

1. [---][C]aecilianu[s][---]

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Manganaro suggested that this was perhaps from a seat in the theatre

Digital identifiers:

TM 175775

EDCS 6100278

Bibliography

1888-. L'année épigraphique: revue des publications épigraphiques relatives a l'antiquité romaine.. *L'année épigraphique : revue des publications épigraphiques*

relatives a l'antiquité romaine.. At 1989.0341p

Manganaro, G. 1989. Iscrizioni Latine nuove e vecchie della Sicilia. *Epigraphica*. 51: 161-196. At 177 no.52 fig.56

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